

1 **Traceological analysis of the stone tools from the Middle Pleistocene Rhinoceros butchery site of San**
2 **Pedro in Rizal, Kalinga (Philippines)**

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8

9 Abstract

10 Ongoing excavations at Rizal, Kalinga in northern Luzon have yielded a rich stone tool assemblage associated
11 with an almost-complete disarticulated skeleton of *Rhinoceros philippinensis*, together with other fossil fauna
12 remains attributed to an extinct megafauna including *Stegodon*. All finds originate from a clay-rich bone bed that
13 was dated to between 777-631,000 years ago using electron-spin resonance methods (ESR), while the
14 rhinoceros has been directly dated to 709,000 years ago. This discovery provides secure evidence for the earliest
15 colonization of the Philippines and suggests that overseas dispersal across Island Southeast Asia by early
16 hominins took place already during the early Middle Pleistocene.

17 This research presents a traceological analysis of the function and uses of the stone tools associated with the
18 rhinoceros and investigate whether they were used for butchering the said animal and/or for other activities
19 conducted at the site that may indicate whether the site was used as a temporary camp for early hunter-gatherers
20 or was rather a so-called 'kill site'.

21

22 Introduction

23 An early presence of hominins in the Philippine archipelago has long been postulated since the 1950s, with the
24 reporting of presumably 'Palaeolithic' industries consisting of chopping tools and flakes together with
25 Pleistocene megafaunal remains from surface finds and excavations in the Cagayan River basin of northern
26 Luzon (Koenigswald 1958; Dizon and Pawlik 2010; Ingicco et al. 2018). Although field research was conducted
27 since more than 60 years ago, no convincing association between megafauna and lithic industries was found
28 there, and no secure absolute dates of both fossil fauna and lithics could be obtained, until very recently.

29 While previous data have suggested a presence of early humans in the Philippines at around 50-67,000 years,
30 the recent finds of a unique stone tools assemblage together with a rhinoceros skeleton exhibiting clear signs
31 of butchery at Rizal, Kalinga in northern Luzon now predate this assumption by over 600,000 years (Ingicco et
32 al. 2018). This also strengthens the proposed antiquity of the similar but currently undated stone tool
33 assemblages found in Luzon (Koenigswald 1958; Pawlik and Ronquillo 2003; Pawlik 2004; Teodosio 2005;
34 Dizon and Pawlik 2010) and in Cagayan de Oro, Mindanao (Neri 2006). Together with similarly old lithic
35 artefacts in association with early hominin remains on Flores Island and Sulawesi (Brumm et al. 2010; van den
36 Bergh et al. 2016a, 2016b), the materials from Rizal provide evidence for the capacity of early hominins to cross
37 the open sea reaching the oceanic islands of Southeast Asia beyond Wallace/Huxley's Line as early as 700,000
38 years ago.

39 The Kalinga lithic assemblage is diverse in its techniques, technology and final products, and appears similar to
40 the stone tool assemblage from Arubo 1 in Nueva Ecija, previously described also by the proponent (Pawlik
41 2004). All artefacts originated from the same location in close proximity to the skeletal remains of the rhinoceros
42 (Unit F). Except for the two possible hammer stones, all artefacts lack patination and have a rather fresh
43 appearance, indicating that any transport and reworking were minimal at best (Fig. 1). The knapping strategies
44 were oriented towards short and unorganized core reduction, resulting in non-standardized flake morphologies
45 and dimensions, typical for the Early Palaeolithic of this region.

46 The proposed project will apply traceological methods of experimental microscopic use-wear analysis using low
47 and high power optical light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, and X-ray microprobes in order to
48 identify tool function, uses, and the activities conducted by the earliest tool makers in the Philippine Islands. It
49 will identify whether all tools were used in the process of butchering the rhinoceros or for other activities, if
50 any, that have been conducted at the site. More concretely, it will shed light on the question of whether the
51 Rizal site was a so-called 'kill site' where the animal were just hunted (respectively scavenged) and their meat
52 removed from the carcass, or if it can be considered a camp site where a hominin group stayed longer, possibly
53 as indicated by the presence of other animal remains from stegodon, deer, tortoise, lizard at the site. Finding
54 actual traces of typical camp activities on the stone tools from Rizal would, therefore, contribute to the
55 identification of the oldest human settlement in the region.

56

57 Background

58 The Philippine archipelago lies at a geographically strategic location between the mainland and islands of
59 Southeast Asia. It straddles two distinct biogeographic zones, with Palawan located on the north-eastern edge
60 of the Sunda Shelf and the main islands of Luzon, the Visayas and Mindanao situated in Wallacea. While a
61 posited land bridge either in the Late Pleistocene (Fox 1970; Cranbrook 2000) or more likely in the Middle
62 Pleistocene (Heaney 1985; Pawlik & Ronquillo 2003) possibly facilitated the colonization of Palawan by Sundaic
63 Island species, including perhaps hominins, most of the Philippines has never been physically linked to the
64 Sundaic region and a sea crossing has always been needed to reach its islands (Heaney 1993; Oliver & Heaney
65 1996; Esselstyn et al. 2010). The archipelago's palaeogeography points hereby towards a migratory path of early
66 hominins entering the Philippines maybe together with the Middle Pleistocene megafauna from Pleistocene
67 Sundaland, i.e. present-day Borneo via either Palawan and Mindoro, and/or the Sulu archipelago, Mindanao,
68 Eastern Visayas towards Luzon, and perhaps also from Sulawesi via the southern arc of islands of the Celebes
69 Sea to southern Mindanao. Landscape reconstructions have shown that to reach Luzon would have required at
70 least two open sea crossings (Pawlik and Piper 2019) and suggest that a form of early watercraft technology
71 perhaps already existed during that time. Similar arguments for such boat technology have been posited for the
72 initial presence of hominins on Flores Island which has been dated to c. 700,000-900,000 BP (van den Bergh
73 et al., 2009; Brumm et al. 2010).

74 The oldest sites in the Philippines have been identified on the island of Luzon. The island possesses an
75 impoverished insular faunal community dominated by successful open sea migrants that once reached Luzon
76 and diversified to produce the high endemism characteristic of remote archipelagos in Wallacea (Heaney 1986;
77 1993; 2002; Jansa et al. 2006; Morwood & van Oosterzee 2007; Oliver & Heaney 1996). Surveys of northern
78 Luzon have produced an archaic vertebrate fauna containing giant tortoise (*Geochelone*), proboscideans
79 (*Stegodon* and *Elephas*), bovines, cervids, suids and rhinoceros (*Rhinoceros luzonensis*, resp. *philippinensis*). Isolated
80 fossil finds that could date to more than 700,000 years ago have been found in the Mindanao and Visayan areas
81 of the Philippines. Those fossil remains have occasionally been reported as being associated with surface
82 collections of lithic artefacts labelled as the Cabalwanian, and the presence of hominins in the Middle
83 Pleistocene of the Philippines has been postulated for the Cagayan Valley in northern Luzon since the 1950s

84 (Koenigswald 1958; Fox 1978; Pawlik and Ronquillo 2003; Dizon and Pawlik 2010). Although the lithic
85 artefacts were found on or close to the surface of eroded terraces and not in direct context with the fossil
86 animal remains, Fox (1978) suggested based on the inferred chronological associations between the stone tools
87 and the extinct vertebrate faunas that the lithic assemblages were produced by a precursor to modern humans
88 who had reached Luzon during the Middle Pleistocene. Recent research near the old sites of Robert Fox have
89 confirmed this assumption. In 2013, a survey of the Cagayan Valley, near the Rizal Municipality (Kalinga
90 Province), led to the discovery of a concentration of vertebrate bones and stone artefacts scattered on the
91 surface. The Rizal site, located at 17° 33' 45.0318" N, 121° 33' 35.7372" E, has been excavated annually since
92 2014, in collaboration with AdMU's Dept. of Sociology and Anthropology and has resulted in the discovery of
93 *in situ* megafauna and associated stone artefacts (Ingicco et al. 2018). The substrate consists of the upper part
94 of the Awidon Mesa Formation, a 400-m thick sequence of alluvial stream deposits with mainly sandstones and
95 claystones intercalated with volcanoclastic and pyroclastic layers. These sediments were deposited on an alluvial
96 fan system in braided streams of the paleo-Chico River resulting from an uplift in the Central Cordillera to the
97 west (Mathisen & Vondra 1983).

98 The main excavation within a 16 m² area is conducted at the head of a modern, dry stream valley, north of a
99 small hill and down to a maximum depth of 2 m (Ingicco et al. 2018). Excavations revealed a total of 7.5 m of
100 stratigraphy comprising four main sedimentary units. An almost-complete disarticulated skeleton of *Rhinoceros*
101 *philippinensis* was found embedded in the basal sediments lying across the base of an erosional channel that was
102 filled with up to 3.25-m thick mudflow which covered the bones, along with 57 stone tools and fossils of other
103 animals (*Geoemydidae*, *Varanus cf. salvator*, *Stegodon cf. luzonensis* and *Cervus cf. mariannus*). The archaeological layer
104 is conformably overlaid by an approximately 1.15m thick, sterile, cross-bedded fluvial sands followed by a 2.5m
105 thick silty pedogenized layer with rhyzoliths (Ingicco et al. 2018). The stone artefacts are situated in close
106 context with faunal remains and could be securely identified as contemporaneous. Three different dating
107 methods were applied directly to the rhinoceros remains and the embedding sediments, Single crystal
108 ⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar dating was applied to plagioclase crystals from above and below the archaeological layer, while
109 Electron-spin-resonance and Uranium-series dating were conducted on the enamel of the rhinoceros's right
110 maxillary third premolar. The tooth yielded an age of 709,000 ± 68,000 years which is bracketed by the Argon
111 dates from below and above the find layer of c. 1,000,000 years and c. 701,000 years, respectively (Ingicco et al.
112 2018).

113 About 300km south of Rizal in Central Luzon, a small assemblage of more formal lithic artefacts of possible
114 Early Palaeolithic origin was recovered at the site of Arubo, in the municipality of General Tinio in Nueva Ecija
115 (Pawlik 2002). The assemblage included several Early Palaeolithic tool types, including a handaxe (Pawlik 2009;
116 Pawlik & Ronquillo 2003; Dizon & Pawlik 2010). Although the Arubo artefacts were recovered from or just
117 below the ground surface and without chronological association, their technological similarity with several Early
118 Palaeolithic assemblages dated to between c. 0.6-1ma BP across Southeast Asia and southern China (van
119 Heekeren 1972; Bartstra 1984; Soejono 1984; Sémah et al. 1992; Leng Jian & Shannon 2000; Yamei et al. 2000;
120 Simanjuntak et al. 2001; Derevianko et al. 2016; Huang 1989; Schick & Dong Zhuan 1993; Zeitoun et al 2013;
121 Wang et al. 2014) suggest a similar age for Arubo, and is now further supported by the recent finds in northern
122 Luzon (Ingicco et al. 2018). From the Arubo assemblage and selected artefacts from the Fox excavation in
123 Espinosa, Kalinga (Fox 1978) stem the only published traceological studies of such old assemblages to date,
124 conducted by Pawlik (2004) and Teodosio (2006). They were able to identify a number of activities on various
125 materials that were conducted at both archaeological sites, such as processing of bamboo and other hard plant
126 material, as well as bone working and butchering.

127 Following the existence of an initial hominin occupation of the Philippines at c. 700kya, there appears to be a
128 remarkable absence of prehistoric sites until 70kya, and the continuation of hominin occupation from the early
129 Middle Pleistocene until the Late Pleistocene remains completely unknown. Currently, the earliest upper

130 Pleistocene evidence for a human presence stems from Callao Cave in the Peñablanca karst limestone region
131 of northern Luzon. In 2007, the third metatarsal of an enigmatic hominin, which has been initially ascribed to
132 an anatomically modern human, was found during the excavation of the cave and was directly dated using U-
133 Series ablation to $66,700 \pm 1000$ BP. Continuation of the excavation in 2011 and 2015 delivered several
134 phalanges, molars and premolars of at least two more individuals, now assigned to a new species, *Homo luzonensis*
135 (Détroit et al. 2019). Laser ablation U-Series of one human tooth as well as associated animal bones yielded
136 dates of c. 50ka BP, somewhat younger than the date from the human MT3 (Grün et al. 2014; Détroit et al.
137 2019). By this time, the Middle Pleistocene megafauna found in Kalinga appears to be mostly extinct. The
138 faunal assemblage associated with the hominin remains of Callao suggests that only deer, pigs, and bovines
139 survived into the Late Pleistocene. No stone tools or other artefacts were found in the same context as the
140 fossils, thus questioning the hominin character of the fossils, although the authors claimed a presence of cut
141 marks identified on some animal bones and considered that the Callao specimen was a tool-using hominin
142 (Piper & Mijares 2007; Détroit et al. 2019).

143 The earliest securely dated lithic artefacts in the archipelago have a minimum age of over 30ka cal BP, and were
144 retrieved from Bubog 1 Cave on Ilin Island in Mindoro where they were recovered from layers together with
145 consumed marine shells and fish remains (Pawlik et al. 2014; Neri et al. 2015; Pawlik and Piper 2019). They
146 were moreover associated with the currently oldest bone tool found in the Philippines, identified as a fishing
147 gorge used for bait fishing of larger carnivorous fish (Boulanger et al. 2018; Pawlik and Piper 2019). In Palawan,
148 lithic assemblages found in Tabon Cave have been associated with charcoal radiocarbon-dated to $30,500 \pm$
149 1100 BP (Fox 1970), while direct Uranium-series dates on the remains of several individuals, all assigned to
150 *Homo sapiens*, recovered from the cave during excavations in the 1960s by Robert Fox (1970; 1978), and in
151 2000 in a re-investigation of the cave by the National Museum of the Philippines and the Muséum national
152 d'histoire naturelle, Institut de Paléontologie Humaine, place them between 16 ka and 47 ka BP, although with
153 a large margin of error (Détroit et al 2004).

154 Identified Early Palaeolithic assemblages, labelled as Cabalwanian, appeared as scattered surface finds from
155 several locations along the Cagayan River in northern Luzon (Koenigswald 1958; Fox and Peralta 1978; Pawlik
156 and Ronquillo 2003; Dizon and Pawlik 2010), in Nueva Ecija, Central Luzon at the site of Arubo, and at the
157 Huluga site in Cagayan de Oro, Mindanao (Neri 2006). While the assemblages from northern Luzon and
158 Mindanao are mainly composed of simple Mode 1 pebble tools, the Arubo assemblage incorporates unifacial
159 and bifacial Mode 2 artefacts, including a handaxe, choppers, and retouched flakes (Pawlik & Ronquillo 2003;
160 Pawlik 2009; Dizon & Pawlik 2010). The presence of large amounts of chert in close vicinity might suggest that
161 Arubo was also frequented for the acquisition of raw material and tool production. Variation in core preparation
162 and reduction is indicated by the presence of several cores, including a core on a large flake and a so-called
163 horse-hoof core, similar to Early Palaeolithic assemblages in Java (Koenigswald 1936; van Heekeren 1972;
164 Bartstra 1984; Soejono 1984; Sémah et al. 1992; Simanjuntak et al. 2001). Multiple uses and curation were
165 recognized in the conducted microscopic use-wear analyses (Pawlik 2002; Teodosio 2006). Interestingly, the
166 prehistoric tool makers at Arubo and at Kalinga appear to have shared the same chert sources for tool
167 manufacturing, thus indicating a potentially similar age (Teodosio 2006; Dizon and Pawlik 2010; Ingicco et al.
168 2018).

169 On the mainland, several Early Palaeolithic sites in Vietnam, Thailand and in South China dated to between
170 0.6-1.0 million years ago BP delivered handaxes and other bifacial and unifacial forms similar to Arubo (Huang
171 1989; Xiang Anqiang 1990; Xie Guangmo 1990; Schick & Dong Zhuan 1993; Leng Jian & Shannon 2000;
172 Yamei et al. 2000; Zeitoun et al 2013; Derevianko et al. 2016). Unfortunately, the Arubo site was heavily
173 disturbed prior to excavation, caused by the dredging of a fishpond. Although that activity eventually led to the
174 discovery of the site, most of the artefacts were recovered on or close to the ground surface, making it
175 impossible to get a reliable chronometric date. However, the morphology of the Arubo assemblage is

176 distinctive and characteristic for the Early Palaeolithic in east Asia. If the typological and technological similarity
177 of the lithic artefacts from Arubo with those assemblages from dated contexts on the Mainland and in Indonesia
178 means that they also share a similar age, then this supports the Middle Pleistocene colonization of Luzon Island
179 by a hominin much older than *Homo luzonensis* that has so far evaded identification.

180 Although the Early Palaeolithic record of the Philippines is still fragmentary, and evidence for the presence of
181 Middle Pleistocene hominins needing further verification, several assemblages from Luzon Island, especially
182 the recent find of a rhinoceros skeleton with possible human induced modifications, strengthen the argument
183 for a potential migration of hominins into the oceanic part of the Philippines around 0.7-1.0 million years ago
184 (Dizon & Pawlik 2010; van den Bergh 2016b; Ingicco et al. 2018). Despite the limit and difficulty in undertaking
185 intensive archaeological research in much of the conflict-affected southern Philippines, particularly the Sulu
186 Sea area, where even more valuable finds and interpretations are expected to come out, significant conclusions
187 could be sufficiently drawn from archaeological data coming from the islands of Palawan, Mindoro, and Luzon
188 with regards to human migration, behavioural, and technological developments in the Philippines from the Late
189 Pleistocene to the mid-Holocene, as well as in comparison with similar narratives emerging across Southeast
190 Asia (Bulbeck 2008; Piper 2015; Shipton et al. 2019).

191

192 Methods

193 Traceology or microscopic use-wear analysis is an efficient method for the reconstruction of prehistoric
194 activities and technologies carried out with prehistoric tools. Since Sergei A. Semenov's pioneering work in the
195 1950s and its consequent translation to English (Semenov 1964), microscopic use-wear analysis has been
196 adopted and developed by prehistoric archaeologists worldwide (e.g. Anderson 1980; Hayden 1979; Kamminga
197 1977; Keeley 1980; Odell & Odell-Vereecken 1980; Plisson 1983; Unrath 1982; Unrath et al. 1986; Vaughan
198 1985, and many others). Working from a pool of data accrued via experimental replication of presumed
199 prehistoric working activities using replicas of lithic artefacts, analysts are able to identify wear patterns and
200 surface alterations on lithic artefacts found in the archaeological record. Macro- and microscopic comparison
201 of wear traces on experimental and archaeological lithic material then allows for the likely function(s) of
202 prehistoric stone tools to be determined.

203 In addition to invasive traces of wear visible on the tool's surface, identification of residues adhering to the
204 artefact is integral to the reconstruction of past activities. Residues of the worked materials (e.g. blood, starch
205 grains, phytoliths, epidermal tissue, parenchyma, ochre, pyrite, copper) sometimes remain on the functional
206 parts of the artefact. Approaches to the identification of these residues has been discussed by a number of
207 authors (e.g. Fullagar 1998; Gechter-Jones & Pawlik 1998; Hardy & Garufi 1998; Pawlik 2004b; Haslam 2006;
208 Lombard 2005; Loy 1983, 1990; Rots & Williamson 2004; Torrence & Barton 2006). Although the antiquity of
209 the lithic assemblage from Rizal might not have permitted organic residues to preserve, residue studies at the
210 similarly early hominin site of Mata Menge, Flores Island, have demonstrated that there is a potential to find
211 microscopic remains of former contact materials, for instance residues associated with fire-striking (Brumm
212 2006).

213 Traceology is mainly applied on stone tools, but the methods are increasingly adapted to study prehistoric tools
214 made of organic materials like bone and shell (Semenov 1964; Barton et al. 2009; Langley and O'Connor 2015;
215 Pawlik et al. 2015; Winiarska-Kabacinska and Kabacinski 2016). It applies optical and digital low and high
216 power microscopy with stereo-microscopes and reflected light microscopes as well as laser-scanning
217 microscopes and scanning electron microscopes coupled with micro-analysers, to detect and identify the

218 different kind of wear traces that can appear on the functional parts of prehistoric tools (Keeley and Newcomer
 219 1977; Hayden 1979; Anderson 1980; Keeley 1980; Odell and Odell-Vereecken 1980; Plisson 1983; Vaughan
 220 1985; Evans and Donahue 2008). Subject to use-wear analysis are the various patterns of edge damage,
 221 especially the diagnostic proximal and distal cross-sections of scars (Hayden 1979; Vaughan 1985; Figure 1*),
 222 and structural alterations of the tools' surfaces, the so-called "micropolishes", as well as striations indicating the
 223 motion of a tool versus the worked material. In addition, residues on the surfaces of stone tools can give clues
 224 about their former use. In this study, 21 lithic artefacts directly associated with the rhinoceros remains and
 225 dated to c. 709kya were subjected to traceological analysis applying the low-power method (Odell and Odell-
 226 Vereecken 1980), using a zoom-stereomicroscope Olympus SZX-9 with a magnification of 6x-57x, and the
 227 high-power method (Keeley 1980), using a reflected-light microscope Olympus BXFM-LWD with Differential-
 228 Interference-Contrast attachment and 100x-500x magnification and a portable Olympus BHMJ-LWD with
 229 Differential-Interference-Contrast attachment and 110x-440x magnification. The microphotographs were
 230 taken with Nikon D-5000 and Canon G9 digital cameras and Promicron microscope adapter system. Post-
 231 processing of the microphotos was conducted with Helicon Focus and Adobe Photoshop. Low power images
 232 are labelled with letters (A, B, C,...), High power images are numbered (1, 2, 3,...). Prior to microscopic analysis,
 233 the artefacts were carefully cleaned in an ultrasonic tank using a solution of dishwashing soap and distilled water
 234 and rinsed with 70% alcohol solution and air-dried.

235

236

237 Figure 1, Cross-sections of edge-scarring (after Hayden 1979 and Vaughan 1985)

238

239 Results

240 Twenty-one lithic artefacts from the San Pedro site in Rizal, Kalinga (NM Code II-2014-J1; Ingicco et al. 2018)
 241 have been subjected to microscopic use-wear analysis. One or more potential used areas were identified on
 242 eleven artefacts. In general, the observed wear traces are only weakly developed, and the interpretation of use
 243 has to be taken with some caution. Seven artefacts appear to have been used in various activities on harder
 244 material and medium hard material (Table 1). Four others had traces that could have been produced by some
 245 taphonomic agents and the rest had no or no identifiable traces. Longitudinally oriented actions could be
 246 identified in two cases while transverse motion was performed with at least one artefact. Two artefacts show

* Figure numbers are tentative

247 traces suggesting multiple activities, no. 733 was used in transverse and longitudinal actions on a harder organic
 248 material, while no. 765 appeared to have been used on two different materials, hard and medium hard, possibly
 249 plant. Although the traceological analysis does not permit a direct association of the observed wear traces with
 250 the butchering marks on the rhinoceros, it can be noted that the traces found on nos. 402 and 676 suggest that
 251 those tools had a contact with bone. Artefact no. 051 permitted only an identification as “used”, due to weakly
 252 developed and less diagnostic traces. All lithic artefacts with use traces are flakes. Only two are larger than 50
 253 mm, while five are small sized specimen, in distinctive contrast to the often propagated large-sized
 254 chopper/chopping tool “industries” of Southeast Asia and more similar to assemblages from Sangiran and
 255 Ngandong in Java and (van Heekeren 1972; Fox 1978; Soejono, 1982; Bartstra 1992; Corvinus 2004; Keates
 256 and Bartstra 2000; Pawlik 2002).

Artefact no.	Potentially Used Areas	Traces			Activity	Contact material
		Low Power	High Power	Use		
51	1	Y	Y	Y	?	?
128a	3	Y	Y	N	-	-
128b	1	Y	N	N		
211	0	N	N	N		
274	0	N	N	N		
376	0	Y	N	N		
388	0	Y	N	N		
400	0	N	N	N		
402	1	Y	N	Y	longitudinal	Hard organic (bone?)
460	1	Y	N	N		
479	1	Y	N	Y	transverse	Hard organic
520	0	N	N	N		
599	1	Y	N	N		
610	0	N	N	N		
611	0	N	N	N		
674	1	Y	N	Y	longitudinal	Hard organic
676	2	Y	Y	Y	?	Hard organic (bone?)
677	0	N	N	N		
733	2	Y	Y	Y	multiple	Hard organic
765	2	Y	Y	Y	multiple	Medium (plant mat.) and hard organic
775	0	N	N	N		

257
 258 Table 1: Results of the traceological analysis

259

260 Description of wear traces

261 No. 051: This flake was made of Chalcedony and exhibits a multi-strike platform remnant. Fungal
 262 contamination is visible along the edges (Figure 051). The lateral edges are post-depositionally removed. The
 263 very thin edge of its distal end is irregularly denticulated by a series of crescent break scars of different sizes
 264 (Figure 051: A, B). It remains difficult to distinguish whether they were caused by use or are non-use related
 265 wear. High power analysis reveals a polish-like surface alteration along the ventral edge (Figure 051: 1, 2). It
 266 appears rather undeveloped and does not show diagnostic features or striations, except for a high reflection
 267 and its reticular distribution on elevated areas of the tools’ microtopography. Basically, the same polish
 268 development is visible on the dorsal edge, however in somewhat lesser distribution (Figure 051: 4, 5). While
 269 similar weakly developed polishes appear on the entire surface, they clearly appear denser towards the edge.
 270 While this might suggest the use of this artefact, a further determination of this function was not possible.

271

272 Figure 051: Artefact no. 051 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

273

274 No. 391: This artefact appears rather as a shattered piece than a flake, with mostly steep and irregular edges and
 275 splintered at the base (Figure 391). The partially reddish color and some hairline cracks in the silex might
 276 indicate exposure to heat. The lateral edges are mostly without wear traces, and only single small scars are visible
 277 that are rather of taphonomic origin than use-related. Potentially used areas are the triangular tipped end (PUA
 278 I) and one shoulder featuring the only sharp-angled edge on this tool (PUA II). The immediate tip is defined
 279 by a shear fracture leaving a slightly crescent break (Figure 391: A). Its edge to the dorsal face has a small but
 280 intense scarring with multiple stepped micro negatives with DST and DHG terminations, similar to a second-
 281 edge-row feature that abraded the immediate edge and part of the ridge towards the tip (Figure 391: B). Also
 282 slight gloss seems to appear along the scarred edge (Figure 391: B2). Using high power analysis, a bright
 283 reflecting polish bevel becomes visible (Figure 391: 1, 2). Numerous striations, longitudinal and across the
 284 polish cause a rather rough surface structure with smooth areas between that exhibit some micropitting (Figure
 285 391: 1, 2 Detail).

286 Slight abrasion appears also on the opposite side (Figure 391: A Detail), together with a thin bright reflecting
 287 polish bevel. Similar to Pos. 1 and 2, short transverse striations appear on the polish surface (Figure 391: 6).
 288 Since no further damage is visible on the other two edges of the triangular tip, it is possible that only the tipped
 289 distal end was used. The morphology of edge wear and polish suggests a harder organic material, e.g. bone. The
 290 limited distribution of the wear traces makes a transverse oriented activity like engraving more likely than an
 291 activity that applied rotation. The dorsal part of the tip served as main contact area, with occasional changes to
 292 ventral. PUA II has a slightly denticulated appearance due to several compression ripples on dorsal. Some small
 293 irregularly shaped scars are visible on dorsal and ventral, their origin remains indeterminable (Figure 391: C,
 294 D). Along the immediate edge, a similar micropolish as along PUA I can be observed on ventral (Figure 391:
 295 3, 7). It is not continuously developed along the edge but appears on the entire area C (Figure 391: 4). On the
 296 inner ripple, a slight gloss similar to Area B can be observed (Figure 391: E). High power analysis reveals a
 297 dense but rather weakly developed polish covering the ripple. Few striations can be observed in transverse
 298 direction relative to PUA II (Figure 391: 5, 5Det). This polish in the interior but somewhat elevated part of the

299 tool suggests a rather shallow working angle using PUA II. PUA II was certainly used on the same material as
300 PUA I in a dominantly transverse, scraping activity, and very likely within the same working context.

301

302

303 Figure 391: Artefact no. 391 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

304

305 No. 402: This Quartzite pebble fragment exhibits a denticulated, fairly straight edge (Figure 402). Several steep
306 scars and CBs have serrated the edge, they are predominantly located on the steeper angled Face B. The coarse-
307 grained rock hampers further analysis and a secure identification of the wear traces. The scars certainly derive
308 from a contact with hard matter. While this contact doesn't have to be necessarily use-related, their rather
309 regular appearance might suggest an intentional contact, except for the single CB in the middle of the edge
310 which could result from post-depositional damage, for instance trampling (Figure 402: A). In addition, some
311 crystals along the potential working edge appear slightly rounded/abraded (Figure 402: B). As a potential
312 activity, cutting/sawing through a harder matter like bone can be considered. High power analysis was not
313 applicable due to the coarse-grained structure of the artefacts and no developed edge polish could be observed.

314

315 Figure 402: Artefact no. 402 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

316

317 No. 479: This is a small andesitic pebble fragment (Figure 479) with multiple fractures and a potentially modified
 318 edge (Figure 479: A). Due to the coarseness of the rock material, it is not clearly identifiable whether its sequence
 319 of poorly defined steep negatives was intentionally created or was just the result of natural reworking processes.
 320 However, secondary microscars appear along the immediate edge. Also, their shapes are not well defined
 321 because of the coarse-grained rock, but their presence might indicate a contact with a harder material (Vaughan
 322 1985), possibly from a scraping/planing activity (Figure 479: B). No distinct rounding is observed along the
 323 edge and the activity performed was only for a rather brief period. High Power analysis didn't not reveal any
 324 wear-related micropolish.

325

326

327 Figure 479: Artefact no. 479

328

329 No. 519: An asymmetrical triangular flake with a pointed distal end and a pronounced bulb of percussion. It is
 330 made of a coarse-grained silex with the appearance of milky quartz. Its lateral edges are rather thick with a 90
 331 degrees angle, with PUA I having a convex and PUA II a slightly concave form. No significant edge wear is

332 visible with the bare eye. The distal end (PUA III) appears rather blunt due to the right angle of both lateral
 333 edges and appears more like a burin end (Figure A). Diffuse scars with shallow terminations near the tip (Detail
 334 A) might indicate frontal and lateral pressure applied on the immediate tip. This might be use-related, however
 335 the slightly “fresher” surface of this part of the edge could also suggest a post-depositional cause. No clearly
 336 defined wear traces appear along the lateral edges. The few diffuse microscars observed have formed on the
 337 facets of the edge (B, C) rather than the adjacent dorsal and ventral surfaces where only single and less invasive
 338 shallow scars with DFR termination appear along the medial part of PUA II (D).

339
 340 Figure 519: Artefact no. 519 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

341
 342 674: This artefact is a large split cortex fragment of a quartzitic pebble, possibly caused by a thermal fracture
 343 (Figure 674). The reddish discoloration of the outer surface against the yellowish-light brown color of the
 344 interior suggests exposure to heat prior to fragmentation. A few irregular larger removals dorsal on the distal
 345 end are not diagnostic of use and are probably post-depositional (Figure 674: A). However, along one lateral
 346 edge appears a row of crescent breaks (CB) and steep scars with hinge termination (PST-DHG). Such scars are
 347 typically caused by hard contact materials and might have been caused by longitudinal motion, for instance
 348 sawing (Figure 674: B).

349

350 Figure 674: Artefact no. 402 with locations of observed traces

351

352 676: This artefact appears as a small, elongated flake shatter ending in a hinge termination (Figure 676). It was
 353 made of a homogenous chert, features pseudo-burin negatives along one lateral edge (Figure 676: A) and a
 354 frontal step break on a fissure plane (Figure 676: B). No wear traces were observed along the sharp and
 355 unmodified edges. The other edge and much of the dorsal surface are covered by water worn cortex. High
 356 power analysis revealed a highly reflecting 'sediment polish' that covers the entire surface of the artefact and
 357 hampers analysis (Figure 676: 2). No diagnostic use polish is observed along the lateral edges. Only the
 358 immediate tip of the 'pseudo burin' displays small polish spots on elevated parts of the artefacts'
 359 microtopography. They exhibit a bright reflection, diffuse frontal longitudinal striations with a faint reticular
 360 distribution on dorsal (Figure 676: 1) and smooth domed surfaces with micropitting on ventral (Figure 676: 3).
 361 The traces are too weakly developed to securely determine a use, at best a contact of the tip with a harder
 362 organic material such as bone could be considered.

363

364 Figure 676: Artefact no. 676 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

365

366 733: This pointed chert fragment appears as slice of a core (Figure 733). Rather unusual for a lower palaeolithic
 367 artefact, there are two regular elongated and parallel negatives visible which would even suggest removal of
 368 bladelet-like flakes (Figure 733: E). Two potentially used areas (PUA) in the form of lateral edges are recognized.
 369 Both lateral edges exhibit edge scarring suggesting use of this artefact. PUA I is a steep-angled concave edge in
 370 the pointed half of the artefact. Few larger scars with step termination are truncated by secondary negatives
 371 with DST and DHG cross-sections, similar to a second-edge-row feature after Vaughan (1985), suggesting a
 372 hard contact material (Figure 733: A). The negatives appear on the steep dorsal side of the edge.

373 The convexly curved lateral edge (PUA II) carries along its distal part and towards the tip a sequence of CB
 374 and less steep PST-DFR negatives provide a slightly denticulated appearance (Figure 733: B), followed by larger
 375 and more intrusive scars with PST-DFR cross-section in the medial part (Figure 733: C). No second-edge-row
 376 appears on Location B aside from single microscars on the proximal edge, but the immediate scarred edge
 377 appears slightly rounded at 20x magnification (Figure 733: B Detail). On Location C, a partial second-edge-row
 378 with some stepped microscars points to a harder contact material. All negatives are on ventral suggesting a
 379 transversal, scraping motion with dorsal as contact surface, but also an activity different from the one found
 380 on PUA I. A row of microscars with CB cross-sections appears towards the thick and cortex-covered
 381 ('proximal') end (Figure 733: D), in groups alternating from dorsal to ventral. Considering the thin and fragile
 382 edge in this part, they might be an unintentionally created abrasion or related to handling.

383 High Power analysis shows only weakly developed polishes near the tip. A blunt smooth-pitted-polish (after
 384 Vaughan 1985) with greasy appearance has formed at the immediate tip on ventral (Figure 733: 1), while a thin
 385 moderately reflecting polish bevel-like accumulation of polish spots with similar texture is visible along PUA I
 386 (Figure 733: 2). Applying higher magnification only revealed isolated polish spots with bright reflection and a
 387 fluidal, smooth surface with few diffuse micropits (Figure 733: 4). No developed micropolish is visible along
 388 the ventral side of PUA II (Figure 733: 3). On the dorsal face, no developed use-wear is observed both on PUA
 389 I and II. Possibly the abrasive contact removed particles of the immediate working edge before polish could
 390 develop.

391

392 Figure 733: Artefact no. 733 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

393

394 765: This is a trapezoidal flake from a bipolar core made of andesite (Figure 765). Potentially used areas are the
 395 concave lateral edges, labelled as PUA I and II. PUA I has a slightly concave shape with a v-shaped cross-
 396 section of the edge. Diffuse shallow DFR negatives appear on both faces together with a slight rounding of the
 397 immediate edge (Figure 765: A-C). They potentially resulted from a scraping activity on a plant material of
 398 medium hardness, like woody vines or bamboo. PUA II is irregularly concave reduced by several wider CBs
 399 (Figure 765: D). However, they don't seem to be use-related but appear to have been caused by trampling or a
 400 similar post-depositional effect.

401 The coarse and grainy structure of the flake prevented the formation of developed micropolishes. Only isolated
 402 polish spots are visible where the crystal faces were parallel to the ventral and dorsal faces. On ventral, Figure
 403 765: 1 shows a bright reflected and slightly domed polish formation with micropitting and diffuse striations
 404 transverse to the edge of PUA I, while dorsal on the same tip micropolish spots with micropitting and diffuse
 405 longitudinal striations appear (Figure 765: 4). Polish spots that appear along the ventral edge of PUA I (Figure
 406 765: 2, 3) and to a somewhat lesser extent on dorsal, might point towards contact with a harder organic material
 407 like bone.

408

409 Figure 765: Artefact no. 765 with locations and microphotos of observed wear traces

410

411 Discussion and Conclusion

412 At Kalinga, the presence of the carcass of a rhinoceros with butchery marks on several of its bones directly
 413 raises the question of whether the rather small tools associated with Kalinga were used to carve the animal
 414 (Ingicco et al., 2020). 21 of the lithic artefacts from the Kalinga site appeared suitable for microscopic toolmark
 415 analysis. One or more potentially used areas were identified on eleven artefacts from the Kalinga site. In general,
 416 the observed wear marks are rather weak, so the interpretation of use should be treated with some caution.
 417 Seven artefacts appear to have been used during various activities on harder and medium-hard material (Table
 418 Results). In two cases, longitudinal movements were detected, while at least one artefact showed transverse
 419 movements. Two artefacts show traces indicating multiple activities; No. 733 was used for transverse and
 420 longitudinal movements on harder organic material, while No. 765 was used to work two different materials, a
 421 hard and a medium-hard, possibly plant material. Although the trace analysis does not allow a direct attribution
 422 of the observed wear marks to the butchery marks on the rhinoceros, it can be stated that the traces found on
 423 artefacts no. 402 and 676 indicate that these tools came into contact with bone. No. 051 could only be identified
 424 as "used" due to its weak and less diagnostic traces. Nos. 02 and 765 also show some traces that do not appear
 425 to be caused by use and are more likely to be the result of trampling. The analysis thus made it possible to
 426 distinguish post-depositional, taphonomic traces on the tools from San Pedro from the traces of former tool
 427 use. Post-depositional movements of the archaeological material as part of a mudflow as well as trampling were
 428 as well identified at the Kalinga site, as some of the rhinoceros bones had some corresponding abrasive marks
 429 (Ingicco et al., 2018). The morphology of the Kalinga assemblage still needs to be discussed, particularly their
 430 generally small sizes. Only two artefacts with use-wear traces are larger than 50 mm, which is in clear contrast
 431 to the large-sized chopping tools often propagated in Southeast Asia and and more similar to the assemblages
 432 from Sangiran and Ngandong on Java (van Heekeren 1972; Fox 1978; Soejono, 1982; Bartstra 1985; Corvinus
 433 2004; Keates and Bartstra 2001).

434

435

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437 References

- 438 Anderson, P., 1980. A Testimony of Prehistoric Tasks: Diagnostic Residues on Stone Tool Working Edges.
 439 *World Archaeology* 12, 2, pp. 81-194.
- 440 Barton, H., P. J. Piper, R. Rabett, and I. Reeds. 2009. Composite hunting technologies from the Terminal
 441 Pleistocene and Early Holocene, Niah Cave, Borneo. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 36, 1708–1714.
- 442 Bartstra, G., 1984. Some remarks upon: fossil man from java, his age, and his tools. In: van de Velde, P. (Ed.),
 443 *Prehistoric Indonesia: A Reader*. Foris, Dordrecht, Netherlands, 121–162.
- 444 Bartstra, G.J. 1992. Pacitan and Sangiran, and Java Man's tools. In P. Bellwood (Ed.), *Man and His Culture*. New
 445 Delhi: Books and Books, pp. 93-103
- 446 Brumm, A. 2006. Fire-making using a stone 'strike-a-light' in the Soa Basin of Flores, Indonesia. Indo-Pacific
 447 Prehistory Association Bulletin 26: 168-170.
- 448 Bulbeck, D. 2008. An integrated perspective on the Austronesian diaspora: The switch from cereal agriculture
 449 to maritime foraging in the colonization of Island Southeast Asia. *Australian Archaeology* 67, 31-52.
- 450 Cnats, D., Perrault, K., Stefanuto, P., Dubois, L., Focant, J. and Rots, V. 2018. Fingerprinting glues using HS-
 451 SPME GC×GC-HRTOFMS: a new powerful method allows tracking glues back in time. *Archaeometry*.
 452 10.1111/arc.12364. Derevianko, A.P., N.Kh. Su, A.A. Tsyvbankov, & N.G. Doi. 2016. *The origin of bifacial*
 453 *industry in Southeast Asia*. Novosibirsk: IAET SB RAS Publishing.
- 454 Corvinus, G. 2004. Homo erectus in East and Southeast Asia, and the questions of the age of the species and
 455 its association with stone artifacts, with special attention to handaxe-like tools.
- 456 Détroit, F., Dizon, E. Falgueres, C., Hameau, S., Sémah, F., Ronquillo, W.P. 2004. Upper Pleistocene homo
 457 sapiens from Tabon Cave (Palawan, the Philippines). *Human Paleontology and Prehistory* 3, 705–712.
- 458 Détroit, F., A. Mijare, J. Corny, G. Daver, P. Piper, et al. 2019. A new specie of Homo from the Late Pleistocene
 459 of the Philippines. *Nature* 568, 181-186.
- 460 Dizon, E. Z. & A. Pawlik 2010. The Lower Palaeolithic Record in the Philippines. *Quaternary International* 223-
 461 224, 444-450.
- 462 Esselstyn, J.A., C.H. Oliveros, R.G. Moyle, A.T. Peterson, J.A. McGuire & R.M. Brown, 2010. Integrating
 463 phylogenetic and taxonomic evidence illuminates complex biogeographic patterns along Huxley's
 464 modification of Wallace's Line. *Journal of Biogeography* 37(11), 2054-66.
- 465 Evans, A., and R. Donahue. 2008. Laser scanning confocal microscopy: A potential technique for the study of
 466 lithic microwear. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 35, 2223-2230.
- 467 Fox, R.B., 1970. The Tabon Caves. Manila: National Museum of the Philippines.
- 468 Fox, R. B. 1978. The Philippine Palaeolithic. In: Ikawa-Smith, F. (ed.), *Early Palaeolithic in South and East Asia*.
 469 Paris: Moutton, 59-85.
- 470 Fullagar, R. (ed.), 1998. - *A Closer Look. Recent Australian Studies of Stone Tools*. Sydney University Archaeological
 471 Methods Series 6.
- 472 Gechter-Jones, J. & Pawlik, A., 1998. Ein absolut datiertes Mehrzweckgerät der frühen Bronzezeit:
 473 Feuerschläger und Meissel. *Archäologie im Rheinland* 1997, pp. 33-35.
- 474 Grün, R., S. Eggins, L. Kinsley, H. Moseley, and M. Sambridge 2014 Laser ablation U-series analysis of fossil
 475 bones and teeth. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 416:150-167.
- 476 Hardy, B. L. & Garufi, G. T., 1998. Identification of woodworking on stone tools through residue and use-
 477 wear analyses: experimental results. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 25,2, pp. 177-185.

- 478 Haslam, M. A., 2006. *Archaeological Residue and Starch Analysis. Interpretation and Taphonomy*. Ph.D. thesis, University
479 of Queensland, School of Social Science.
- 480 Hayden, B., (Ed.) 1979. *Lithic Use Wear Analysis*. Academic Press, New York.
- 481 Heaney, L., 1993. Biodiversity patterns and the conservation of mammals of the Philippines. *Asia Life Sciences*
482 2(2), 261-74.
- 483 Huang, Weiwen 1989. Bifaces in China. *Human Evolution* 4 (1): 87-92.
- 484 Ingicco, T., G.D. van den Bergh, C. Jago-on, J.-J. Bahain, M.G. Chacón, N. Amano, et al. 2018. Earliest known
485 hominin activity in the Philippines by 709 thousand years ago. *Nature* 557: 233–237.
- 486 Ingicco, T., Reyes, M.C., de Vos, J., Belarmino, M., Albers, P.C.H., Lipardo, I., Gallet, X., Amano, N., van den
487 Bergh, G.D., Cosalan, A.D., Bautista, A., 2020. Taphonomy and chronosequence of the 709 ka Kalinga
488 site formation (Luzon Island, Philippines). *Scientific Reports* 10, 11081.
- 489 Jansa, S. A., F. K. Barker & L. R. Heaney 2006. The pattern and timing of diversification of Philippine endemic
490 rodents: evidence from mitochondrial and nuclear gene sequences. *Systematic Biology* 55, 1, 73-88.
- 491 Kamminga, J., 1977. A functional study of use-polished eloueras. In Wright, R. (Ed.), *Tools as Cultural Markers*.
492 *Prehistory and Material Culture Series* 12, Canberra, Australian Institute of Aboriginal Studies, pp. 205-212.
- 493 Keates, S.G., and Bartstra, G.J., 2000. Observation on Cabengian and Pacitanian artifacts from Island Southeast
494 Asia. *Quartär* 51/52, 1–27.
- 495 Keeley, L.H. 1980. *Experimental Determination of Stone Tool Uses*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- 496 Keeley, L.H., and M.H. Newcomer. 1977. Microwear Analysis of Experimental Flint Tools: A Test Case. *Journal*
497 *of Archaeological Science* 4, 29-62.
- 498 Koenigswald, G. H. R. von 1958. Preliminary report on a newly discovered Stone Age culture from Northern
499 Luzon, Philippine Islands. *Asian Perspectives* 2, 69-71.
- 500 Langley, M., and S. O'Connor. 2015. 6500-Year-old Nassarius shell appliques in Timor-Leste - technological
501 and use wear analyses. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 62, 175–192.
- 502 Lombard, M., 2005. Evidence for hunting and hafting during the Middle Stone Age at Sibudu Cave, Kwa-
503 Zulu-Natal, South Africa: A multi-analytical approach. *Journal of Human Evolution* 48, pp. 279-300.
- 504 Loy, T. H., 1983. Prehistoric blood residues: detection on tool surfaces and the identification of species of
505 origin. *Science* 220, pp. 1269-1271.
- 506 Loy, T. H., 1990. Prehistoric organic residues: recent advances in identification, dating and their antiquity. In
507 Wagner, W. & Pernicka, E. (Eds.), *Archaeometry '90: Proceedings of the 27th International Symposium on*
508 *Archaeometry*, Heidelberg, pp. 645-656.
- 509 Mathisen, M. & Vondra, C. The fluvial and pyroclastic deposits of the Cagayan Basin, northern Luzon,
510 Philippines - an example of non-marine volcanoclastic sedimentation in an interarc basin. *Sedimentology*
511 30, 369–392 (1983).
- 512 Morwood, M. J. & P. van Oosterzee 2007. *The discovery of the Hobbit: the scientific breakthrough that changed the face of*
513 *human history*. Sydney: Random House.
- 514 Neri, L.A., 2006. A possible Paleolithic site in Northern Mindanao. *Hukay. Journal of the University of the Philippines*
515 *Archaeological Studies Program* 10, 25–37.
- 516 Odell, G. H. & Odell-Vereecken, F., 1980. Verifying the reliability of lithic use wear assessments by "blind
517 tests": The low power approach. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 7, pp. 87-120.
- 518 Oliver, W. L. R., and L.R. Heaney, 1996. Biodiversity and conservation in the Philippines, *International Zoo News*
519 45(3), 329-37.

- 520 Pawlik, A. 2002. Is there an Early Palaeolithic in the Philippines? New approaches for lithic analysis in the
 521 Philippines. In: M. Horrocks & P. Sheppard (eds.), *Australasian connections and new directions: proceedings of the*
 522 *7th Australasian Archaeometry Conference*. Research in Anthropology and Linguistics 5. Auckland: University
 523 of Auckland, 255-270.
- 524 Pawlik, A.F., 2004. The Palaeolithic site of Arubo 1 in Central Luzon, Philippines. *Bulletin of the Indo-Pacific*
 525 *Prehistoric Association* 24, 3–12.
- 526 Pawlik, A.F., 2009. Is the functional approach helpful to overcome the typology dilemma of lithic archaeology
 527 in Southeast Asia? *Bulletin of the Indo-Pacific Prehistoric Association* 29, 6–14.
- 528 Pawlik, A.F. and W.P. Ronquillo, 2003. The Palaeolithic in the Philippines. *Lithic Technology* 28(2), 79-93.
- 529 Pawlik, A.F. and P.J. Piper, 2019. The Philippines from c. 14,000 to 4,000 cal. BP in Regional Context. *Cambridge*
 530 *Archaeological Journal* 29(1), 1-22.
- 531 Pawlik, A., P. J. Piper, R. Wood, K. Lim, M. Faylona, A. Mijares, and M. Porr. 2015. Shell tool technology in
 532 Island Southeast Asia: an early Middle Holocene *Tridacna* adze from Ilin Island, Mindoro, Philippines.
 533 *Antiquity* 89, 292–308.
- 534 Plisson, H. 1983. Etude fonctionnelle des outillages lithiques préhistoriques par l'analyse des micro-usures,
 535 recherche méthodologique et archéologique. Doctoral thesis, Université de Paris I.
- 536 Piper, P.J., 2015. Human cultural, technological and adaptive changes from the end of the Pleistocene to the
 537 mid-Holocene in Southeast Asia, in *The Routledge Handbook of Bioarchaeology in Southeast Asia and the Pacific*
 538 *Islands*, eds. M. Oxenham & H.R. Buckley. London: Routledge.
- 539 Piper, P.J. & A.S.B. Mijares 2007. A preliminary report on a Late Pleistocene animal bone assemblage from
 540 Callao Cave, Peñablanca, Northern Luzon, Philippines. Unpublished report, Archaeological Studies
 541 Program, University of the Philippines/National Museum of the Philippines.
- 542 Rots, V. & Williamson, B. S. 2004. Microwear and residue analyses in perspective: the contribution of
 543 ethnoarchaeological evidence. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 31, 1287-1299.
- 544 Schick, K. D. & D. Zhuan, 1993. Early Paleolithic of China and Eastern Asia. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 2, 22–
 545 35.
- 546 Sémah, F. A.-M. Sémah, T. Diubiantono & H. T. Simanjuntak 1992. Did they also make stone tools? *Journal of*
 547 *Human Evolution* 23, 439–446.
- 548 Semenov, S. A., 1964. *Prehistoric Technology*. Bath, Adams and Dart.
- 549 Shipton, C., S. O'Connor, C. Reepmeyer, S. Kealy & N. Jankowski. 2019. Shell Adzes, Exotic Obsidian, and
 550 Inter-Island Voyaging in the Early and Middle and Holocene of Wallacea. *Journal of Island and Coastal*
 551 *Archaeology*. DOI: 10.1080/15564894.2019.1581306.
- 552 Simanjuntak, T., B. Prasetyo, & R. Handini (eds.), 2001. *Sangiran: Man, Culture, and Environment in Pleistocene Times*.
 553 The National Research Centre of Archaeology, EFEO dan Yayasan Obor Indonesia.
- 554 Soejono, R.P. 1982. *New data on the Paleolithic industry in Indonesia*. 1er Congres International de Paleontologie
 555 Humaine, Nice, pp. 78–92.
- 556 Soejono, Raden P. 1984. *Prehistoric Indonesia*. In P. van de Velde (ed.), *Prehistoric Indonesia. A Reader*, 49-78.
 557 Dordrecht: Foris.
- 558 Teodosio, Sharon F. R. 2006. A Functional Analysis of the Arubo Stone Tools. Master's thesis, University of
 559 the Philippines, Archaeological Studies Program.
- 560 Torrence, R. & Barton, H., (Eds.) 2006. *Ancient Starch Research*. Left Coast Press Inc., California.
- 561 Unrath, G., 1982. *Die Funktionsbestimmung geschlagener Steinwerkzeuge anhand ihrer mikroskopisch erkennbaren*
 562 *Gebrauchsspuren*. Unpublished Master's thesis, Universität Tübingen.

- 563 Unrath, G., Owen, L. R., van Gijn, A., Moss, E. H., Plisson, H. & Vaughan, P., 1986. An evaluation of micro-
564 wear studies: A multi-analyst approach. In Unrath, G. & Owen L. (eds.), *Technical Aspects of Micro-wear*
565 *Studies on Stone Tools. Early Man News* 9/10/11. Tübingen, Archaeologica Venatoria.
- 566 Van den Bergh, G.D., H.J.M. Meijer, D.A. Rokhus M.J. Morwood, K. Szabó, L.W. van den Hoeke Ostende,
567 T. Sutikna, E.P. Saptomo, P.J. Piper & K.M. Dobney, 2009. The Liang Bua faunal remains: A 95 k. yr.
568 sequence from Flores, East Indonesia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 57, 527–37.
- 569 Van den Bergh, G. D., Bo Li, A. Brumm, R. Grün, Dida Yurnaldi, M.W. Moore, I. Kurniawan, R. Setiawan, F.
570 Aziz, R. Roberts, Suyono, M. Storey, E. Setiabudi.5 and M.J. Morwood, 2016a. Earliest hominin occupation
571 of Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Nature* 529, 208–211.
- 572 Van den Bergh, G. D., Y. Kaifu, I. Kurniawan, R. Kono, A. Brumm, E. Setiyabudi, F. Aziz, and M.J. Morwood,
573 2016b. Homo floresiensis-like fossils from the early Middle Pleistocene of Flores. *Nature* 534, 245–248.
- 574 Van Heekeren, H.R., 1972. *The Stone Age of Indonesia*. Second edition. The Hague: Martinus Nijhoff.
- 575 Vaughan, P., 1985. *Use-wear analysis on flaked stone tools*. University of Arizona Press.
- 576 Wang, Y., H. Cheng, R.L. Edwards, X. Kong, X. Shao, S. Chen, J. Wu, X. Jiang, X. Wang & Z. An 2014
- 577 Winiarska-Kabacinska, M., and J. Kabacinski. 2016. Flint tools for bone and antler adzes production at the
578 Early Mesolithic site Krzyz Wielkopolski 7 (Western Poland), *Quaternary International*,
579 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2016.02.015>
- 580 Xiang Anqiang. 1990. Palaeolith discovered in the Lishui Basin, the Dong-ting Lake region. *Southern Ethnology*
581 *and Archaeology* 3 :249-70.
- 582 Xie Guangmao. 1990. Relation between the stone tools from Baise and the Lower Palaeolithic cultures from
583 South and Southeast Asia. *Southern Ethnology and Archaeology* 3:237-47.
- 584 Yamei Hou, R. Potts, Yuan Baoyin, Guo Zhengtang, A. Deino, Wang Wei, J. Clark, Xie Guangmao and Huang
585 Weiwen. 2000. Mid-Pleistocene Acheulean-like stone technology of the Bose Basin, South China. *Science*
586 287: 122
- 587 Zeitoun, V., H. Forestier, M. Rasse, P. Auetrakulvit, J. Kim, and C. Tiamtinkit. 2013. The Ban Don Mun
588 artifacts: a chronological reappraisal of human occupations in the Lampang province (Northern Thailand).
589 *Journal of Human Evolution* 65, 10–20.
- 590